

What Would I Do with 300,000 USD?

If I received 300,000 USD (~102,000,000 HUF), I would know what to do with it... I would create the **Sanaterra Animal Sanctuary**.

A thought has been with me for many years. At first, it was just a sigh when I saw a solitary, excluded primate living in a group behind glass walls in a zoo. Later, I noticed an increase in my concern when I visited areas where there were no longer glass walls for visitors, but many issues persisted: water, shade, care, attention, environmental enrichment, responsibility, and quality food were lacking. Then the sigh and thought became a plan, which is no longer a dream, but a ready-made concept "put on paper". All I need is money. For example, **300,000 USD**.

And yes, **I would know what to do with it**. My aim is not to have a large number of animals gathered for viewing (like a zoo), but to provide an opportunity for as many animals as possible to find hope again. **To have a place where it is not important whether it is useful, but that it lives and feels.**

What would Sanaterra Animal Sanctuary (SAS) be?

A **climate-resilient sanctuary, which is small-scale, scalable, sustainable**. A "handkerchief-sized piece of land" **in the Dinaric Alps** – e.g. in a water-secure, climate-stable region of Bosnia and Herzegovina or **in Brčko** with a special status – where there is room for a few good-quality enclosures, a few sheds and pens, a loving, carefully selected house, a small vegetable garden. But in its soul: **home, shelter, second chance. A "full life" in a "truncated" world.**

SAS is not an animal collection – it is a purpose-driven sanctuary based on ethics, compassion, and resilience.

- A place where **rescued** (meat) **poultry, older hens, and newly hatched cockerels** can experience sunlight for the first time in their lives.
- Where **elderly, orphaned, or rescued goats and sheep** will find lifelong companionship and green pastures.
- Where **baboons and macaques** can live in small but carefully designed, social enclosures, **no longer waiting in laboratories** for their final placement,

ethanized due to lack of space, or **as inbred, elderly, “commercial” species** in zoos, or **as “remnants” left over from illegal imports**, facing a hopeless tomorrow. These sensitive relatives of ours, prone to behavioural disorders in chaotic situations, **will be at risk in many zoos in the future** (including those in nearby Southern Europe and the Middle East) **due to the lack of drinking water, electricity, food, and unbearably hot temperatures.**

(This project was initiated by the same interdisciplinary team that developed the **ZooShield Protocol ([ZooShield Protocol – Global Zoo Evacuation Strategy under Polycrisis Conditions](#))**).

- We would also be happy to welcome “problematic” primates that zoos – for more reason – cannot or do not want to integrate into their existing population. By engaging with **marginalized individuals**, it is possible to foster deep and valuable relationships that benefit both humans and animals, while ensuring adherence to safety regulations.
- Where **injured, ex-laboratory small-sized marmosets** (and tamarins) do not wait for their last day alone in a dusty terrarium – but can rest in pairs, small groups or “families”, among lush vegetation, trees, and shadows.
- Where some **birds**, who were perhaps **unable to return to the wild precisely because of humans**, can find a home and a mate, and perhaps not among the rocks of the cliffs, but on the ground or in a basket of a decorative tree, lay eggs and raise healthy offspring (which we can then release).
- Where **people can learn that ethical thinking, minimalism, trauma sensitivity, and respect for nature** are not just empty words – but daily practice, while they can also **“heal” themselves through “therapy” with animals.**

This would be **Sanaterra**. A holier version of Earth – as the name suggests. A **gentle little place**, not trying to save the world – just giving life to a few discarded, unnecessary creatures with compassionate conservation. There are many shelters, but far fewer **sanctuaries**, and even fewer that provide a final, haven exclusively **for marginalized animals.**

What would 300,000 USD be enough for?

This is not a “cost”, but primarily a value, **every penny is purpose-bound and impact-oriented. Here is the distribution of the total amount** (subject to variations based on the plot and house infrastructure):

Item	Cost (USD)	Comment
Plot and house	120,000	In an accessible, mountainous, water-secure area (e.g. Travnik–Jajce–Jablanica or the special status Brčko), preferably with existing and convertible outbuildings, with usable spaces from the house (e.g. community space, toilets, guest or volunteer accommodation, space for an indoor primate enclosure. Large houses are more typical in Bosnia and Herzegovina, which would provide this opportunity. In this case, the price of the property is typically more expensive than the indicated amount, but this results in a cost reduction in the cost lines of (1.) special indoor enclosures; (2.) the community space and (3.) the accommodation of volunteers-guests!).
Construction and renovation of enclosures (5–6 pcs.)	60,000	Non-human primates (e.g. Hamadryas and/or Anubis baboons, Rhesus and/or Javan macaques, marmosets), pigs, goats, poultry, native flightless birds.

Item	Cost (USD)	Comment
Special indoor enclosures and boxes (for primates)	15,000	Heating, water supply, cleanability, isolation. (Quarantine room.)
Water- and Energy Independence (drilled well, rainwater harvesting, solar panels, wood-burning stove)	25,000	Building a basic sustainability system that does not depend on service providers for everything in the long term creates, cheaper operational security.
Creation of a community space, small museum and library, educational trail	6,000	Awareness programs, dissemination of knowledge, library and conversational activities.
Accommodation for volunteers and guests (min. 3-4 people)	9,000	Establishing profitable but ethically priced hospitality to maintain the shelter and accommodate volunteers who come for several weeks.
Animal transportation, veterinary care for the first year	30,000	Condition assessment, medications, vaccinations, use of animal transport services.
Reserve and start-up fund for year 1	35,000	Feed, maintenance (buffer), basic salary for one person.

Total: 300.000 USD

We would use the amount saved for any item for the following:

1. Buying or permanently renting a used but good condition (category B) vehicle suitable for transporting animals and feed (e.g. van/minibus/station wagon or minivan).
2. Hiring and paying additional staff.
3. Building a new enclosure.

What would this place give back to the world?

- **Life** for those exploited, useless – but not domestic – animals that the world – laboratories, zoos, slaughterhouses, many people – has already “written off.”
- An **opportunity** for people who themselves carry trauma (this is still a current problem in Bosnia and Herzegovina due to the Yugoslav war), but who want to heal through a “personal” connection with animals.
- **Hope** for all those who no longer believe that it is possible to live and do life differently along a moral compass.
- A **model**: to show that it is possible to provide quality shelter even on a small footprint. Moreover, this model **replicability in post-crisis or semi-peripheral regions**.
- To offer an **example** to similar regions in other countries (especially from the Balkans to Central Asia), where there are many lives to save – but few credible intentions and truly functioning structures. **Soon, examples will be crucial due to the global polycrisis challenges** (see **ZooShield Protocol**).

What will happen if the 300,000 USD target is not achieved?

Then there will still be Sanaterra. Only smaller, with fewer enclosures, more work, slower – but with the same determination. Because this is not a “project” – but an internal command, a “drive.”

In case of partial funding, the sanctuary will launch in Brčko District as a compact but fully functional pilot site.

What happens if the amount exceeds 300,000 USD?

Then Sanaterra will be bigger. We will adopt more animals as family members, we will build bigger and more enclosures, we will give more people jobs and livelihoods, we will try to provide SOS help to more organizations in difficult situations, we will rescue animals from more distant destinations, and we will be able to welcome more lonely people with attention and love for animals.

If you would like to be a part of our ethical, compassionate, and resilient mission...

- If you would like to help with the **cost of an enclosure, pen, shed, solar collector**, feed, or veterinary care, **write to us!**
- If you have a **company, community, school, acquaintance** who is looking for a **CSR partner – let's talk!**
- If you know someone who is just **looking for an honest, good, clean cause** or for whom animals really represent value – **show them this page.**
- If you want your child to experience compassion firsthand – **Sanaterra will be waiting.**

Sanaterra does not exist yet, but it already has a written "map", strategy, serious concept, and budget plan. It has a story and a heart. **It is just waiting for a chance!**

Thank you for reading. If Sanaterra has already found a home in your heart, write to us – or just save the thought for later. **Because every life matters – and every help resonates somewhere.**

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